

AUTOMED 2024

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für die Medizin

Proceedings

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Editorial

AUTOMED--24: Advances in Automation and Control in Medical Technology

As part of the 12th Symposium on „Biological and Medical Systems“ of the International Federation of Automatic Control (IFAC) the 17th Interdisciplinary Workshop AUTOMED-24 was co-organized. AUTOMED workshops which have been held every 18 months since 1997, are regularly initiated by the AUTOMED technical committee, which is jointly run by the Society for Measurement and Automation Technology (GMA) and the German Society for Biomedical Technology (DGBMT) in the VDE/VDI to promote the exchange of ideas between engineers, doctors and physicists working in the fields of automation technology and medicine.

These conference proceedings contain the 24 abstracts of the poster presentations and illustrate the diversity of research topics, the high level of research expertise and the innovation potential of automation in medicine for the field of medical technology.

Exciting research results were presented ranging from intelligent instruments and new materials to AI-based data analysis for innovative diagnostic procedures and therapeutic approaches. These advances have the potential to improve patient care with better treatment precision and set new standards in medical technology.

Further topics relating to AUTOMED can be found in the proceedings of the IFAC BMS-24 Symposium published at IFAC PapersOnline 58, 2024: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/ifac-papersonline/vol/58/issue/24>

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Table of Contents

No	Title	Authors	Page no	DOI
1	Artificial Pancreas under stable MPC: including the Physical Activity effect	<i>Licini, N. Sonzogni, B. Abuin, P. Previdi, F. Gonzalez, A.H. Ferramosca, A.</i>	1-2	10.5281/zenodo.14277265
2	Monitoring spontaneous breathing during apnea testing with electrical impedance tomography	<i>Chen, R. Lovas, A. Krueger-Ziolek, S. Bakos, P. Moeller, K.</i>	3-4	10.5281/zenodo.14277323
3	Development of osseointegrative implants with drug delivery function for medical technology	<i>Burger, L. Ulrich, S. Mozaffari-Jovein, H.</i>	5-6	10.5281/zenodo.14277392
4	Multiple Model Predictor for Type 1 Diabetes	<i>Ragni, M. Mongini, P. A. Magni, L. Toffanin, C.</i>	7-8	10.5281/zenodo.14277619
5	Comparing gait parameters for right-convex scoliosis patients with and without brace	<i>Tschirschky, A. Jochim, T. Heinke, A. Żurawski, A. Kiebzaj, W. Malberg, H.</i>	9-10	10.5281/zenodo.14277638
6	On the individualized PIDA tuning for the automatic control of neuromuscular blockade	<i>Schiavo, M. Mendonça, T. Visioli, A</i>	11-12	10.5281/zenodo.14277763
7	Influence of the hybrid process on the vertical bond strength of 3D-printed PEEK implants	<i>Pilehvar, S.1 Heidari, R.1 Mozaffari-Jovein, H.</i>	13-14	10.5281/zenodo.14277794

8	Scoliosis assessment from trunk rotation based on torsobarography using machine learning	<i>Stecher, N. Heinke, A. Żurawski, A. Richter, L. Harder, M. R. Kiebzak, W. Malberg, H.</i>	15-16	10.5281/zenodo.14277806
9	Experimental determination of the transmission behavior of a pressure sensor array for torsobarography in posture analysis	<i>Dohndorf, J. Stecher, N. Heinke, A. Malberg, H.</i>	17-18	10.5281/zenodo.14277836
10	A survey on requirements for safety and control concepts of artificial implantable lungs	<i>Wiertalla, M. Lübke, C. Leonhardt, S. Walter, M. Kopp, R. Kowaleski, S. Stollenwerk, A.</i>	19-20	10.5281/zenodo.14277868
11	Differentiating between structural and functional spinal deformities in children and adolescents using machine learning	<i>Jochim, T. Żurawski, A. Stecher, N. Heinke, A. Kiebzak, W. Malberg, H.</i>	21-22	10.5281/zenodo.14277879
12	A semi-mechanistic mathematical model on the interactions between the ovulatory-menstrual cycle and the metabolic and cardiovascular system	<i>Ramírez-Mazo, C. Gómez-Echavarría, L. Lema-Pérez, L. Röblitz, S.</i>	23-24	10.5281/zenodo.14277917
13	Application of LiDAR and neuromorphic vision in ambient assisted living environments	<i>Huhs, N. Kalashtari, N. Hornberger, C. Kraitl, J. Simanski, O.</i>	25-26	10.5281/zenodo.14278494
14	Targeting fiber tracts in deep brain stimulation: optimal contact configurations	<i>Frigge, A. F. Medvedev, A.</i>	27-28	10.5281/zenodo.14278515

15	An interconnected modular setup for in-vivo evaluation of automated mechanical ventilation	<i>Pfannschmidt, V.</i> <i>Buglowski, M.</i> <i>Grüne, M.</i> <i>Hammer, F.</i> <i>Braun, O.</i> <i>Hütten, M.</i> <i>Kowaleski, S.</i> <i>Schoberer, M.</i> <i>Stollenwerk, A.</i>	29-30	10.5281/zenodo.14278533
16	Vector Representation of Biological Data Using Machine Learning	<i>Karadimas, O.</i> <i>Karvelis, P.</i> <i>Stylios, C. D.</i>	31-32	10.5281/zenodo.14278569
17	Analysis of wireless data transfer methods for subcutaneous medical implants	<i>Gottschalk, L.</i> <i>Müller, S.</i> <i>Bucher, V.</i>	33-34	10.5281/zenodo.14278581
18	Effect of moisture on human tissue impedance measurement using textile electrodes	<i>Petrovs, E.</i> <i>Okss, A.</i> <i>Katashev, A.</i>	35-36	10.5281/zenodo.14278589
19	In vitro test setup for continuous evaluation of oxygenators for extracorporeal circulation	<i>Döcke, A.</i> <i>Mogdans, S.</i> <i>Knomnik, S.</i> <i>Malberg, H.</i>	37-38	10.5281/zenodo.14278601
20	Modular ML-Framework to develop and compare AI models for ARDS classification	<i>Fonck, S.</i> <i>Fritsch, S.</i> <i>Kowaleski, S.</i> <i>Stollenwerk, A.</i>	39-40	10.5281/zenodo.14278618
21	Enhance electrical impedance tomography with magnetic readings	<i>Battistel, A.</i> <i>Özen, A.C.</i> <i>Wilkie, J.</i> <i>Chen, R.</i> <i>von Elverfeldt, D.</i> <i>Möller, K.</i>	41-42	10.5281/zenodo.14278644
22	Photon-counting super-sampled imaging using piezoelectric motors	<i>Fix, N.</i> <i>Helin, H.</i> <i>Billoud, T.</i> <i>von Elverfeldt, D.</i> <i>Goldschmidtboeing, F.</i> <i>Weigt, M.</i> <i>Pichotka, M.</i>	43-44	10.5281/zenodo.14278655

23	Implementation of adapted volume distribution in the basic dynamic Hickling Model	<i>Hofman, J.</i> <i>Bamboschek, J.</i> <i>Fix, N.</i> <i>Möller, K.</i>	45-46	10.5281/zenodo.14278666
24	A multifrequency image reconstruction for electrical impedance tomography to retain tissue spectral information	<i>Battistel, A.</i> <i>Wilkie, J.</i> <i>Chen, R.</i> <i>Möller, K.</i>	47-48	10.5281/zenodo.14278696

